

Studies in Terpenes : Part XLVII α -Terpineol Nitrosobromide.

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The hitherto unknown α -terpineol nitrosobromide and several nitrolamines derived therefrom are described. The N-substituent effects on the mode of chemical shift of the C₇ methyl protons of the nitrolamines detected earlier are operative in this series also.

FOLLOWING up our investigation on γ -terpinene nitroschloride¹ we have now examined ($\pm$)- α -terpineol nitrosobromide.

On treatment with isoamyl nitrite-hydrobromic acid, ($\pm$)- α -terpineol afforded the crystalline adduct, C₂₀H₃₀N₂Br₂O₄, m.p. 117-118°. Based on its IR and PMR characteristics this new derivative is assigned the stereostructure (I). (The adduct is pictured as a *meso* variety though its existence as a *racemic* mixture cannot be excluded). The -NO-stretching frequencies at 11'2, 1'12 and 1226 cm⁻¹ in the IR spectrum support the *trans*-dimeric configuration about the N=N-bond.^{2,3,4} The proton under the nitroso group (δ 5.88) is clearly equatorial showing only small PMR couplings to the adjacent C₃ protons. The assignment of the C₇ stereochemistry with axial bromine and equatorial methyl is based on the field position (δ 1.96) of the C₇ methyl. In a variety of 1-bromo-1-methyl cyclohexane systems it has been reported^{1,5} that the equatorial methyl resonates around δ 1.98 whereas the axial methyl at about δ 1.83. The IR frequency at 710 cm⁻¹ suggests an axial bromine¹. The configurational assignment is also consistent with the free energy difference of these groups ($-\Delta G$ for methyl is 1.8 k cal/mole while $-\Delta G$ for bromine is 0.4 k cal/mole)⁶. Thus we deduce a *trans* incorporation of nitrosyl bromide across the double bond in ($\pm$)- α -terpineol.

With I as the substrate, a series of nitrolamines (II a-i), all optically inactive, were synthesised essentially as previously described for related compounds¹. The PMR characteristics (Table I) support the assigned structures. Earlier examples of the nitrolamines originating from γ -terpinene nitroschloride¹ have shown the chemical shift difference of the C₇ methyl with the nature of the N-substituent. Fresh evidence confirming this trend is now available. Whereas for the secondary amines II e-i the C₇ methyl resonates at δ 1.25, 1.25, 1.25, 1.45 and 1.33, for the tertiary amines II a-d, these occur at the higher field at δ 0.98, 1.03, 0.98 and 1.03 respectively. This differential pattern may be accommodated by the stereochemical implication, viz., in the secondary amines the amino group is small and

TABLE I—M.P. AND PMR δ VALUES OF NITROLAMINES

Nitrolamines@ Kind	Substituents		M.P. °C	Protons			
	R	R'		H ₈	C ₇ Me	C ₉ or C ₁₀ Me	N-OH
IIa	Me	Me	143-144	3.35	0.98	1.20	9.50
IIb	Et	Et	132-133	3.35	1.03	1.23	9.30
IIc	-(CH ₂) ₈ -		160-161*	3.28	0.98	1.20	9.95
IId	-(CH ₂) ₈ -O-(CH ₂) ₂ -		190	3.35	1.03	1.22	10.00
IIe	Et	H	90	3.45	1.25	1.25	—
IIf	n-But	H	111	3.45	1.25	1.25	9.40
IIg	c-C ₆ H ₁₁	H	139	3.42	1.25	1.25	9.20
IIh	Ph	H	155-156**	3.40	1.45	1.23	—
IIi	CH ₃ Ph	H	117	3.45	1.33	1.22	9.83

@ Nitrolamines II a-d and II e-i have respectively (1SR, 4SR)—and (1RS, 4SR)—configurations.

* Lit.⁷ m.p. 159-160°; ** Lit.⁷ m.p. 155-156°.

occupies an axial position with C₇ methyl equatorial, while in the tertiary amines, the amino group is bulkier and orients equatorially, leaving C₇ methyl axial and getting itself shielded by the π -electron system¹.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Recrystallisation of II e was from benzene-petroleum ether (b. p. 40-60°) mixture and other nitrolamines, from aqueous ethanol. TLC was carried out on Merck silica gel G with methanol as solvent. All compounds were TLC pure and gave satisfactory analysis for C, H and N. PMR spectra of compounds II a, c and d were recorded in CDCl₃ containing trace of DMSO-d₆ and all others in CDCl₃.

(±)- α -Terpineol nitrosobromide: A mixture consisting of (±)- α -terpineol (4 g), isoamyl nitrite (6 ml) and ethanol (6 ml) was cooled to 0 to -10°. To this, a chilled solution of hydrobromic acid (48% aq. 4.5 ml) in ethanol (6 ml) was added dropwise with stirring over a period of 15 min. Stirring was continued for an additional 25 min and the product stood at 0-5° for 2 hr. Triturated the mass obtained with cold methanol (25 ml) and then it was collected by filtration (2 g, m.p. 115-117°). Recrystallisation from methanol afforded pure (1S, 1'R, 2S, 2'R, 4R, 4'S)-2,2'-bis-nitroso-1-chloro-8-hydroxy-*p*-methane (I) (1 g); m. p. 117-118° IR (Nujol): 3500, 1226, 1212, 1192 and 710 cm⁻¹; PMR:

δ 5.88 (br, s, W h/2 7Hz, 1H, C₂H), 1.95 (s, 3H, C₁ Me), 1.15 (s, 3H, C₉ or C₁₀ Me), 1.12 (s, 3H, C₆ or C₁₀ Me).

Nitrolamines (II a-i) were prepared by the reaction of the appropriate amine with (±)- α -terpineol nitrosobromide in a manner similar to that described earlier¹. The melting points and relevant PMR data are given in Table (1). For all nitrolamines H_{3eq} resonated as a broad doublet of J=10Hz.

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